

Effect of Cadmium Nanoparticle on the Structure and Enzyme Activities of Gills of Mud Crab *Scylla Olivacea* (Herbst, 1796)

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ABSTRACT

Cadmium has been found to produce wide ranges of biochemical and physiological dysfunctions in humans and animals. In the present study, toxic effects of Cadmium nanoparticle (CdNP) in the gills of mud crab *Scylla olivacea* was evaluated. CdNP (20ppm ppm/kg) induced abnormal structural changes in the gills. In the case of male, gill lamellae showed increased haemal space, destruction of Pillar cells, epithelium dilation and reduction of the thickness of the gill lamellae. In the case of female, complete destruction of haemal canal and haemal cells were observed. CdNP also induced antioxidant enzymes such as Catalase (CAT), Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) and Superoxide dismutase (SOD) in both male and female crabs. Whereas, in the case of mitochondrial enzymes only Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) showed increased activity compared to Succinate dehydrogenase (SDH) and Malate dehydrogenase (MDH) which were recorded decreased activity upon CdNP exposure.

Keyword: Cadmium nanoparticle, *S. olivacea*, Gills, antioxidant enzymes.

INTRODUCTION

Mud crab farming is a recent activity practiced in Bangladesh, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Philippines and Vietnam. In India, crab farming is mainly carried out in West Bengal, Orissa, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka, Goa, Maharashtra and Andaman islands. The mud crabs belonging to the genus *Scylla* are large, fast growing portunids with high commercial value in terms of domestic markets and exports by virtue of their delicacy. Of the three *Scylla* spp. occurring in Indian waters, *S. oceanic*, *S. serrata* and *S. olivacea* are commonly caught. Cadmium (Cd), a toxic and non-essential element frequently used in electroplating, pigments, paints, welding and batteries, which results in both biotic and abiotic environments [1]. Unlike organic compounds, Cd is not biodegradable and has a very long biological half-life [2]. Cd has been found to produce wide ranges of biochemical and physiological dysfunctions in humans and laboratory animals [3]. Many mammalian organs are adversely affected by Cd, which include kidney, liver, testis, lung, pancreas, prostate, ovary, and placenta [4,5] and several studies have illustrated that the testis is exceedingly sensitive to Cd toxicity [6, 7]. During the last two decades, there has been an enormous interest in nanomaterials/nanoparticles due to their novel physical and chemical properties that differ markedly from those of bulk materials. Nanoscale materials find use in a variety of different areas such as electronic, biomedical, pharmaceutical, cosmetic,

energy, environmental, catalytic and material application even though the current use and production of NP are sparse and often conflicting [8]. The forecasted huge increase in the manufacture and use of NP makes it likely that increasing human and environmental exposure to NP will occur. Most attention has thus far been devoted to the toxicology and health implications of NP [9,10,11], while the behavior of NP in the environment [12,13], their ecotoxicology [14] have been less often studied and also no systematic description of the effect of NP on living organisms is yet available. Hence, the present study was aimed to study the CdNP induced histological and biochemical changes in gills of *S. olivacea*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental animals

Fresh samples of male species of *Scylla olivacea* was collected from Pulicate Lake, Pulicate, Tamil Nadu, India. The male crabs were maintained separately in tanks with aerator which was (capacity of 1000 L) filled with filtered (0.45 mm pore) sea water. The sea water was changed periodically and crabs were fed with commercial fish feed. The morphological identification and authentication of species was done by a Scientist from Central Institute of Brackishwater Aquaculture (CIBA), Santhome, Chennai, India.

Toxicity test

The acute semistatic toxicity test was carried out according to the standard methodology described by Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) [15] and the American Public Health Association [16]. Semistatic toxicological bioassays were carried out for 120 h. Different concentrations such as 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 and 120 ppm of CdNP suspension of 100 nm in size (Sigma and Co., Bangalore, India) was injected intraperitoneally per kg of crab weight. A probit analysis was used to estimate the concentration and 95% confidence limits of CdNP that kills 50% of the exposed crab (LD₅₀).

Histology

Experimental crabs were sacrificed and gills (male & female) tissue samples were taken after 2, 4, 6 and 8 d of exposure of 20 ppm/kg of CdNP. The gills were carefully dissected out and fixed in 4% buffered formalin, embedded in paraffin, sectioned (8 mm thickness) on a microtome (Microm, HM330, Heidelberg, Germany), stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H and E) and examined with an Olympus microscope (Tokyo, Japan).

Protein extraction and quantification

A known quantity of gills of both male and female of *S. olivacea* was ground in a pre-chilled mortar and pestle in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) amended with 0.01% polyvinyl poly pyrrolidone and 0.001% ascorbic acid in a ratio of 1:3, filtered and centrifuged (6000 x g) to obtain a clear supernatant. The cell-free supernatant was used as a protein source. Protein content was determined by the method of [17] using bovine serum albumin fraction V (Sigma Chemical Co., Bangalore) as a standard.

Catalase (CAT) activity

Catalase activity was determined in gills of both male and female colorimetrically according to [18]. The rate of disappearance of H₂O₂ is followed by observing the rate of decrease in the absorbance at 240 nm. The CAT activity was calculated as μM of H₂O₂ consumed/min/mg protein and the result were expressed as Units/mg. protein.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity

The SOD activity was estimated by the method of McCord and Fridovich [19]. Cyt-c reduction was measured for 3 min in a 1.5 mL assay mix containing SOD buffer 1 (50 mM KH₂PO₄ and 0.1 mM EDTA at pH 7.8), 10 μM Cyt-c (Sigma), 50 mM xanthine (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany) at 550 nm on a Cary 3E UV/Vis double beam spectrophotometer (Varian, Middelburg, Netherlands) equipped with a temperature controlled cell attached to a water bath. The SOD activity was expressed as Units/mg. protein.

Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) activity

GPx activity was assayed by method of [20]. The reaction mixture consisting of 0.2 mL of EDTA, 0.1 mL sodium azide, 0.1 mL of H₂O₂, 0.2 mL of GSH, 0.4 mL of phosphate buffer and 0.5 mL of homogenate was incubated at 37°C for 10 min, the reaction was arrested by the addition of 0.5 mL of TCA and the tubes were centrifuged at 1500 x g. To the 0.2 mL of supernatant, 3 mL of disodium hydrogen phosphate and 1.0 mL of DTNB were added and the color was read at 420 nm immediately. The activity of GPx was calculated as μM of glutathione oxidize/min/mg protein and the result expressed as Units/mg. protein.

Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) activity

LDH activity was assayed by the method of [21]. A reaction mixture contains 0.1M Potassium phosphate (pH 7.0), 0.01M NADH, 0.1M Pyruvate (Sodium pyruvate) and 0.2 ml diluted

LDH stock solution (10mg/ml). The decrease in absorption at 340nm was followed at 25°C.

Malate Dehydrogenase (MDH) activity

MDH activity was assayed by the method of [22]. An assay mixture contains 9.1ml of 0.1M of potassium phosphate, 0.2ml of 0.01M NADH and 0.5ml of 0.1M oxaloacetic acid. The decrease in absorption at 340nm was followed at 25°C.

Succinate Dehydrogenase (SDH) activity

SDH activity was assayed by the method of [23]. A reaction mixture contains 0.4ml of the tissue extract, 5ml of Phosphate buffer, 0.2ml of sodium succinate, 0.2ml of sodium azide and 0.2ml of DCPIP solution. Absorbance was measured immediately at 610nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The accumulation of toxic compounds within the organism body at lethal levels lead to histological lesion in the body crab, *S. serrata*. The experimental crabs exposed CdNP exhibit histological changes in the gills. Histopathological studies are also useful in evaluating the potential of CdNP, since trace amount of these chemicals which do not bring animal mortality over a given period, were capable of producing considerable organ damage [24].

Fig.1. Effects of CdNP(20ppm) on the anatomy of gills in male *Scylla olivacea* by light microscope on day 8. Scale bar, 10 μm . Ha - Haemocytes; Hc - Haemal canal; Hs - Haemal space. A) Control - Day 2 B) CdNP treated - Day 2; C) Control - Day 4 D) CdNP treated - Day 4; E) Control - Day 6 F) CdNP treated - Day 6; G) Control - Day 8 H) CdNP treated - Day 8.

Fig.2. Effects of CdNP(20ppm) on the anatomy of gills in female *Scylla olivacea* by light microscope on day 8. Scale bar, 10µm. Pc – Pillar cells; Dpc – Disintegrated Pillar cells. A) Control - Day 2 B) CdNP treated - Day 2 ; C) Control – Day 4 D) CdNP treated - Day 4; E) Control - Day 6 F) CdNP treated - Day 6 ; G) Control – Day 8 H) CdNP treated - Day 8.

Fig.3. Catalase activity (CAT) activity in gills of male *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.4. Catalase activity (CAT) activity in gills of female *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.5. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity in gills of male *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.6. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity in gills of female *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.7. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in gills male *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.8. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in gills female *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.12. Malate Dehydrogenase activity in gills of female of *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.9. Lactate Dehydrogenase activity in gills female *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.13. Succinate Dehydrogenase activity in gills of male of *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.10. Lactate Dehydrogenase activity in gills of female *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig.14. Succinate Dehydrogenase activity in gills of female of *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

Fig. 11. Malate Dehydrogenase activity in gills of male *S. olivacea* after exposure of CdNP.

The study of micro-anatomy (histology) of the specific tissue constitutes an important diagnostic tool to observe the histological effects caused by a pollutant. The histological changes may be the manifestation of sick tissue. Gills of the crab, *S. olivacea* were of phyllobranchiate type with a central axis and gill lamellae arranged in two rows on either side. In experimental crab, histological sections of gills showed vacuolization in the gill stem, gill lamellae ruptured, connective tissue cells in the stem damaged, destructed and congestion of haemocytes in the gill lamellae are observed. Pillar cells are damaged. The structure of the gills observed in the present study was well in accordance with earlier reports on different crabs [25]. The thin connective fluidy band

present in between the two gill lamellae is found ruptured which was also observed such changes in the gills of the field crab, *Paratelphusa hydrodromus* on exposure to nickel [26]. Li *et al.* [27] observed structural changes including the swelling and fusion of the lamellae; abnormal gill tips and necrotic lamellae in gills of a giant freshwater prawn, *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* exposed to waterborne copper. The histological techniques are the promising area of research in aquatic toxicology as it gives the real picture of the effects imposed and the involvement of the xenobiotics in either disturbing or destroying the vital organs of living organisms. Many researchers have reported the degenerative changes in selected tissues of the animals in response to pollution by various toxicants [28]; The effect of CdNP (20ppm/kg) on the anatomy of gills of male *S. Olivacea* were presented in Figure 1. Normal crabs displayed usual architecture in all haemal lacunae of the gill lamellae and central shaft (Fig.1A,C,E,G). On day 2 of CdNP exposure, sections of gill lamellae showed increased haemal space with little tissue damage (Fig.1B). Epithelium, pillar cells and haemal vessels were relatively discernible at this stage of the infection. More intense histopathologies were observed in increased day of exposure. On day 4, Pillar cells and epithelium were destroyed, yet there was no evident damage to the central haemal vessel (Fig.1D). On day 6, dilation and reduction of the thickness of the gill lamellae were common as a consequence of the destruction of pillar cells (Fig.1F). On day 8, complete disorganization of pillar cells and haemal canal could be observed in the haemocytes (Fig. 1H). In the case of female crabs, CdNP exposure resulted in progressive disorganization of gills. Similar to male, control female gills displayed usual architecture in all haemal lacunae of the gill lamellae (Fig.2A). On day 2 of CdNP exposure, showed decreased haemal space with little tissue damage (Fig.2B). On day 4, constriction of squamous epithelium was prominent and pillar cells and haemal vessels were not discernible at this stage of the infection. There was a time dependant changes in morphology was evident up on CdNP exposure (Fig.2D). On day 6, haemal canal and haemal cells were destroyed (Fig.2F). On day 8, increased thickness of the haemal canal as a consequence of the destruction of pillar cells and haemal canal could be observed (Fig.2H).

Cadmium nanoparticle (20ppm) exposure resulted in increased Catalase (CAT) activity in the gills of *S. olivacea* than in control crabs. In males, CAT activity started increasing on day 2 and reached peak compared to its control on day 10 of exposure (Fig.3). On the contrary, in the case of female CAT activity started decreasing on day 2 compared to its control but started increasing on day 4 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure. A maximum of upto two fold increase in CAT activity was recorded in both male and female crabs compared to their respective controls (Fig.4). Cadmium nanoparticle exposure resulted in increased Glutathione Peroxidase (GPx) activity in the gills of *S. olivacea* than in control crabs. In males, GPx activity started increasing on day 2 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure compared to its control (Fig.5). Similarly, in the case of female also GPx activity started increasing right on day 2 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure compared to its control (Fig.6). Similarly, increased SOD activity in the gills of *S. olivacea* was recorded compared to control crabs. In general, CdNP resulted in differential response in male and female crabs. In males, SOD activity started increasing in exposed crabs right on day 2 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure (Fig.7). Similarly,

in the case of female also SOD activity started increasing on day 2 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure (Fig. 8).

CdNP modulates activities of key mitochondrial enzymes such as LDH, MDH and SDH. In general, CdNP resulted in increased LDH activity than in control crabs. In males, SDH activity started increasing right on day 2 and reached peak on day 10 of exposure (Fig.9). Similarly, in the case of female also LDH activity started increasing on day 2 and reached maximum on day 10 of exposure. A maximum of upto two and 1.5 fold increase in LDH activity was recorded in male and female crabs respectively compared to their respective controls (Fig.10). In general, CdNP resulted in decreased MDH activity than in control crabs. In males, MDH activity started decreasing right on day 2 compared to control and reached lowest compared to control on day 10 of exposure (Fig.11). Similarly, in the case of female also LDH activity started decreasing on day 2 compared to control and reached lowest compared to control on day 10 of exposure (Fig.12). CdNP also resulted in decreased SDH activity than in control crabs. In males, SDH activity started decreasing on day 2 and reached lowest on day 10 of exposure compared to control (Fig.13). Similarly, in the case of female also SDH activity started decreasing on day 2 and reached lowest on day 10 of exposure. A maximum of upto 1.5 fold decrease in SDH activity was recorded in both male and female crabs respectively compared to their respective controls (Fig.14). With reference to SDH activity, female crab showed more susceptibility to CdNP compared to male crabs.

The present study clearly demonstrated that acute exposure to CdNP led to deterioration of gills of mud crab, which may lend strong support to the conclusion that acute exposure to CdNP results in a cumulative and/or progressive injury and induce antioxidant defence in the gills of both male and female *S. olivacea*.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, we made an attempt to study CdNP induced structural and biochemical changes in gills of mud crab *Scylla olivacea*. Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that CdNP alters both structural integrity and biochemical defence in gills of the mud crab.

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